

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Report on Cycle 3 hackathon
Deliverable number	D33 (Del. Rel. No. D6.6)
Revision	0
Status	Final
Planned delivery date	31/08/2023
Actual date of issue	12/07/2023
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	UiB
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

Report on the conducted knowledge coproduction activities with an update of the coproduction plan.

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WP6

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1 Executive summary

The third hackathon was organized in M20 in Madrid under the lead of the Storms & Ocean theme. Having learned from previous hackathons, the WPs defined their data needs ahead of time, and the Alfred Wegener Institut (AWI), the Max Planck Insitut (MPI), and the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) prepared (i.e., regrided and coarse-grained) the required fields. Furthermore, several online training sessions were provided before the meeting to teach newcomers how to access and analyze model output on irregular grids. A total of 139 scientists and students from 40 different institutes analyzed the Cycle 3 output from ICON and IFS, and frequently were able to report on exciting results. The special challenge du jour was Fisheries and marine biogeochemistry, and the invited stakeholders from France and Senegal were given the opportunity to learn how to analyze SR ESMs and convince themselves of the quality of the simulations.

2 Conclusion & Results

Having built on the experience of the previous two hackathons, this one has probably been the most productive so far, and the key lessons are:

- define, within the WPs, the research goals ahead of time
- prepare the relevant model output in advance
- make sure there are Python experts in every room
- choose a spacious setting, ideally in a university to entrain other interested scientists
- provide ample of opportunity for scientists of different model components to interact

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	yes
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	yes

O2

To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:

(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP6	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify and evaluate key ocean and marine atmosphere features in the SR-ESM simulations of all three development cycles. (O1)	yes
To validate the marine planetary boundary layer representation of the SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	yes
To provide ocean initial conditions for the coupled SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	no
To provide developments towards an ocean mixed layer scheme adequate for SR-ESMs. (O1)	yes
To create numerical tools that generate output streams useful to the planetary boundary layer, ocean mixed-layer and fisheries communities. (O1,O3)	yes

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

Planning started in spring 2022 by polling the task leaders of Storms & Ocean about who would want to host the hackathon and what the preferred location would be. Elsa Mohino of UCM offered the UCM campus and most task leaders preferred Madrid over Copenhagen, Hamburg or Bergen. Contributing factors for the choice were the expected weather, the cost of living, some PIs' positive experiences with previous meetings at UCM, and the existing connection between UCM and the Spanish renewable-energy community.

Figure 1: The 139 attendees captured in a brief moment of stillness.

The meeting started Monday evening and ended Friday at noon; was also opened to two other large climate-science projects, EU H2020 EERIE and the German BMBF Warmworld, both of which rely on the use of high resolution climate models, just like NextGEMS. The meeting logistics was handled excellently by UCM and MPI administrative staff, under the lead of PI Elsa Mohino. The data fields necessary for the work in Madrid were prepared in advance by technical staff at AWI and MPI.

During the hackathon each of the themes was given its own spacious room, and each day there was a common event for all to facilitate cross-disciplinary exchanges: a keynote talk on marine biogeochemistry on Monday (Katja Fennel, Dalhousie) and an icebreaker, a group dinner on Tuesday, a presentation on DestinE (Francesco Doblas-Reyes, Barcelona) on Wednesday and a discussion on the physics of convective clouds on Thursday (Yukari Takayabu, Tokio). We were also able to entrain participants of Belen Rodriguez-Fonseca's MulMod group who, for their investigations of cross-basin interactions, were also given their own room. Friday morning proved to be a thrilling summary of all the findings of the week (see below) and a plenary discussion on how to proceed in the project. Throughout the meeting the outreach group offered interview training for interested scientists.

Most bugs in the ESMs that were discovered in the early phase of NextGEMS had been fixed

for Madrid, and the experience from the first two hackathons helped every WP to prepare the research questions that they wanted to address in Madrid, and the required model output. Thus, the participants were able to investigate a large amount of processes with an unprecedented level of detail. The exciting results are too numerous to list in detail here, and most of them will be presented in the bi-weekly NextGEMS Zoom meetings. Below are simply key results from every theme and the special challenge 'Fisheries'.

4.1 Storms & Radiation

Figure 2: Still of sea salt from an animation of the new ICON aerosol module (P. Weiss).

Highlights were the new aerosol module, and the detailed analysis of shallow and deep convective clouds. The simulated clouds were compared across models and across resolutions, but also to observations. A robust result is that 4.4 km resolution does simulate a more realistic cloud structure than the 9km resolution.

4.2 Storms & Land

- ICON monthly average discharge within observation range
- Rhine discharge event in ICON in February translates to heavy precip

Figure 3: Analysis of river flow and discharge in ICON (van Heerwarden et al.)

During the hackathon it was shown that we now can represent realistically details like river discharge and Alpine microclimates, as well as potential power production by wind farms. The diurnal cycle of precipitation over land also has been improved significantly, as was—in IFS—the representation of blocking events.

4.3 Storms & Ocean

Tropical cyclone rapid intensification (RI) in IFS

Figure 4: Analysis of hurricane intensification rate across different models and resolutions (Vidale et al.)

The ocean is, of course, the most important part of the climate system and a substantial effort was made in Madrid to validate the models' representation of the ocean and the atmospheric boundary layers and the heat, water, and momentum fluxes between them. Most noteworthy results are that, while the ITCZ still has biases similar to the ones found in coarse resolution models, numerous processes that affect the air-sea fluxes start to be represented properly at resolutions of 9 to 4 kilometers. The most exciting of these is probably the simulation of hurricanes at 4km resolution, which comes close to the observations (see Figure 4).

4.4 MULMOD

The project MULMOD is not part of NextGEMS, but it's research focus—tropical modes of coupled variability—is very much of interest to NextGEMS, in particular to WP7 whose work has only now begun. Hence, MULMOD provided valuable early insights into the state of IFS' and ICON's coupled model. Only two 30 year ICON simulations were available, and these two simulations differed mainly in the vertical resolution of the upper ocean (10 levels vs 2 levels in the upper 20m). Given the shortness of the runs it is difficult to draw robust conclusions, but it is obvious that vertical resolution does affect mean sea surface temperature and its variability (fig. 5). Therefore numerous scientists asked for several decades long simulations, even if the resolution would be necessarily lower than 5km.

Difference of means and ratio of variances in SST

- One is COLDER in all tropics except in NTA and western Eq
- *This one has MORE variability The variability is higher and enhanced in the Eastern in summer (JJA) and in central in Winter (DJF) and comparable in the western part in winter

Figure 5: Analysis of SST mean and variance in the simulations with 2 different vertical resolutions (Rodriguez-Fonseca et al.)

NextGEMS *society* theme

The Storms & Society theme works on several fronts on this regard, as you know:

on application communities and integrating potential users

We have a coproduction process going on which will take place on Wednesday, on **renewable energy**. Representatives from different perspectives on the topic are invited, and we will co-decide the type of **storylines** we want to operationalize.

The end goal is to find applications of NextGEMS output data, and decision-making with regards to RE could be on of them.

Join us in the morning to talk to stakeholders or ask for more info!

Rodriguez et al. (2022). User Selection and Engagement for Climate Services Coproduction. *Weather, Climate and Society*, 15 (2), 10.1175/WCAS-22-0112.1

Figure 6: Storms and society flyer to attract potential users from the renewable energy sector to the hackathon

4.5 Storms & Society

Storms & Society organized a focused meeting with members from DestinE and from the Spanish renewable energy community to discuss the needs of the public utilities and wind farm entrepreneurs, and how they can be supported by efforts such as NextGEMS and DestinE. Best practices will be established and the outcomes will be published (see Figure 6).

4.6 Knowledge co-production 'Fisheries'.

Marine ecosystems and fisheries are key applications in NextGEMS. The hackathon brought together first-time users of high-resolution model data from Senegal and France with modellers from MPI. The standard nextGEMS storm-resolving configurations do not include interactive ocean biogeochemistry. Therefore, the ocean biogeochemistry group at MPI has provided an additional ICON ocean simulation including the HAMOCC biogeochemistry module. Analysis showed that with fine resolution the model was able to capture key features of coastal upwelling in sea surface temperature and primary productivity (Fig. 7). A comparison between

the simulated primary productivity and observations of sardinella biomass was made for the three different upwelling regions in west Africa. These unique observations were provided by Senegalese partners. There was a good discussion on how to evaluate the impact of resolving storm scales on marine-ecosystems and fisheries using final 30-year NextGEMS simulations, which will not include biogeochemistry. Ongoing efforts at MPI aiming at 5km coupled ICON simulations including HAMOCC will be helpful here.

The Western African upwelling-fisheries system in ICON/HAMOCC (WP7-nextGEMS)

Figure 7: Overview of analysis of ICON ocean model simulations along the west African coast for marine ecosystem and fisheries applications

5 References (Bibliography)

References

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

Links were established to the Spanish project MULMOD, the German Warmworld, and the EU Horizon Eerie. Furthermore the French and Senegales fishery communities were invited and it

was discussed how SR ESMs can improve the simulation of coastal upwelling and forecasts of fish abundance.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>